

**IN A NIGERIAN ROAD PPP WHICH PARTY SHOULD BEAR THE RISK OF A
NEWLY DISCOVERED ARCHAEOLOGICAL SITE HALTING
CONSTRUCTION? ANALYSIS OF THE LEGAL BASIS FOR ALLOCATION**

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the allocation of risk arising from the discovery of archaeological sites during the construction phase of road infrastructure projects under Public–Private Partnership (PPP) arrangements in Nigeria. The study adopted a doctrinal research methodology, relying on the analysis of relevant Nigerian legislation, as well as policy documents and international PPP guidelines. Comparative insights were drawn from jurisdictions such as the United Kingdom, South Africa, and Australia, where established PPP frameworks provide guidance on the treatment of unforeseen site conditions, including archaeological discoveries. The study found that archaeological discovery risk constitutes a unique category of infrastructure risk, as it arises not from ordinary construction activities but from statutory obligations relating to cultural heritage preservation. The study further found that international best practice generally treats archaeological discoveries as compensation events or shared risks, rather than risks to be fully transferred to private concessionaires. Based on these findings, the study argued that the public authority should bear primary responsibility for archaeological discovery risk in Nigerian road PPP projects, while contractual mechanisms should be established to compensate private concessionaires for delays or additional costs arising from such discoveries. The study recommended the incorporation of explicit archaeological discovery clauses in PPP contracts, the conduct of comprehensive pre-construction archaeological surveys, and the development of standardised PPP contract templates by regulatory authorities.

1 CHAPTER ONE

GENERAL INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

Infrastructure development is widely regarded as a key driver of economic growth and national development. In developing economies such as Nigeria, the demand for infrastructure particularly transportation infrastructure has significantly exceeded the fiscal capacity of government. In response to this challenge, governments increasingly rely on Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs) as an alternative mechanism for financing and delivering infrastructure projects. The Nigerian government has adopted PPP arrangements in several sectors, particularly transportation infrastructure. Examples include the Lekki-Epe Expressway concession, the Lekki Deep Sea Port, and the Highway Development and Management Initiative (HDMI) introduced by the Federal Government.¹

A central element of PPP arrangements is the allocation of project risks between the public authorities and the private partners. The generally accepted principle in PPP projects is that risks should be allocated to the party best able to manage them effectively and at the least cost.² Infrastructure projects often involve significant uncertainties, particularly during the construction phase. One such uncertainty arises when previously unknown archaeological or cultural heritage sites are discovered during excavation or construction works. The discovery of archaeological artefacts may lead to project delays, suspension of works, or modification of infrastructure design in order to protect cultural heritage resources.³ The emergence of such circumstances raises an important legal and contractual question: which party should bear the risk and cost implications of newly discovered archaeological sites in a Nigerian road PPP project? This study therefore examines the allocation of archaeological discovery risk in Nigerian road PPP projects and analyses the legal basis for determining which party should bear such risk.

¹ Infrastructure Concession Regulatory Commission, National Policy on Public-Private Partnerships (Federal Government of Nigeria)

² World Bank, Public-Private Partnership Reference Guide (World Bank 2017)

³ Jeffery Delmon, *Private Sector Investment in Infrastructure* (Kluwer Law International 2009)

1.2 Statement of the Research Problem

Risk allocation is widely recognised as one of the most important elements in the design of PPP contracts. The success or failure of a PPP project often depends on how project risks are distributed between the contracting parties.⁴ While certain risks, such as construction and operational risks, are commonly allocated to private concessionaires, other risks particularly those relating to land use, environmental regulation, or cultural heritage are more complex and difficult to allocate efficiently. The discovery of archaeological sites during construction represents one such risk and are typically unforeseen, occurring despite prior site investigations. When such discoveries occur, construction activities may be halted while archaeological assessments are conducted. In some cases, infrastructure routes may need to be redesigned or relocated in order to protect the discovered heritage site.⁵ These circumstances may result in substantial financial losses, delays in project completion, and disputes between the contracting parties regarding responsibility for additional costs.

In many jurisdictions, PPP contracts address such risks through compensation event clauses or force majeure provisions. However, in Nigeria, PPP frameworks and concession agreements often provide limited guidance regarding archaeological discoveries during infrastructure construction. The absence of clear contractual and legal provisions regarding this issue creates uncertainty for investors and public authorities alike. Consequently, the central research problem addressed in this study is the determination of which party should bear the risk associated with the discovery of archaeological sites during the construction phase of Nigerian road PPP projects.

1.3 Aim and Objectives of the Study

The primary aim of this research is to ascertain which party would bear the risk of a newly discovered archaeological site halting construction in Nigerian road PPP projects and the legal basis for such allocation.

⁴ Irwin T, *Government Guarantees: Allocating and Valuing Risk in Infrastructure Projects* (World Bank 2007)

⁵ World Bank PPP Knowledge Lab, *Risk Allocation in PPP Projects*

The specific objectives of the study are:

1. To analyse the effectiveness of the Nigerian PPP legal and institutional frameworks in the allocation of risks in Nigerian PPP Projects.
2. To examine how archaeological discovery risks are treated in international and Nigerian PPP practice.
3. To evaluate the prospects and challenges in PPP project risk allocation in Nigeria.
4. To propose and recommend legal or contractual reforms required to improve risk allocation in Nigerian PPPs.

1.4 Research Questions

This study seeks to answer the following questions:

1. How efficient are the Nigerian PPP legal and institutional framework in the allocation of risks in Nigerian PPP projects?
2. How are archaeological discovery risks treated in international and Nigerian PPP practice?
3. What are the prospects and challenges in PPP project risk allocation in Nigeria?
4. What legal or contractual reforms are required to improve risk allocation in Nigerian PPPs?

1.5 Scope and Limitations of the Study

This study focuses primarily on road infrastructure PPP projects in Nigeria, with particular attention to the construction phase during which archaeological discoveries may occur. The study examines Nigerian PPP legislation and policies, concession agreements and PPP case studies and international best practices in risk allocation. However, the study does not provide an exhaustive analysis of PPP arrangements in sectors outside transportation infrastructure.

1.6 Significance of the Study

The study contributes to scholarship and policy by providing legal guidance on archaeological risk allocation in PPP projects, improving contractual drafting in Nigerian PPP agreements and enhancing investor confidence in Nigerian infrastructure PPPs.

1.7 Research Methodology

The study adopts a doctrinal legal research methodology through comparative analysis. Data will be gathered both from primary and secondary sources. The study would include comprehensive review of academic literature, legal frameworks and case studies related to PPP projects.

1.8 Chapter Outline

Chapter One: General Introduction

Chapter Two: Conceptual Clarification, Theoretical Framework and Literature Review

Chapter Three: Legal and Institutional Framework for PPPs in Nigeria

Chapter Four: Critical Analysis of Risk Allocation in Relation to Archaeological Discoveries

Chapter Five: Challenges and Prospects

Chapter Six: Findings, Recommendations and Conclusion

2 CHAPTER TWO

CONCEPTUAL CLARIFICATION AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 Conceptual Clarification

2.1.1 Public–Private Partnerships

Public–Private Partnerships (PPPs) have become an important mechanism for financing and delivering infrastructure projects globally. The World Bank defines a PPP as a long-term contractual arrangement between a public authority and a private entity for the provision of public infrastructure or services in which the private party assumes significant financial, technical and operational risks.⁶ This usually entails the public sector's exploitation of private sector skills to make available facilities in the form of projects or services that the market would have less incentive to construct.⁷ The underlying purpose being the provision of infrastructure or services that is usually the responsibility of government or other public institutions.⁸

PPPs typically involve a range of contractual models including but not limited Build-Operate-Transfer (BOT), Design-Build-Finance-Operate (DBFO), and concession agreements. PPPs are usually organized as a special purpose vehicle (SPV), a trust fund, or any other vehicle or associative organization. If it is an SPV, it shall be incorporated as a corporation.⁹ Under these arrangements, the private partner undertakes the financing, construction, operation, and maintenance of infrastructure facilities while the government retains regulatory oversight and ownership of the asset.¹⁰ In Nigeria, PPP arrangements are increasingly utilised to address the country's infrastructure deficit. The Federal Government has implemented PPP projects in sectors such as transportation, power

⁶ World Bank, (n2).

⁷ Sunday Bontur Lugard, 'Risks and Challenges in Public-Private Partnership Projects in Nigeria: A Case Study of the Concession of Murtala Mohammed Airport 2 Terminal (Lagos) to Bi-Courtney Nigeria Ltd' <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/338559875_Risks_and_Challenges_in_Public-Private_Partnership_Projects_in_Nigeria_A_Case_Study_of_the_Concession_of_Murtala_Mohammed_Airport_2_Terminal_Lagos_to_Bi-Courtney_Nigeria_Ltd> accessed on March 17, 2026

⁸ ibid

⁹ Oluwaseun Ayansola and Mayowa Abiru, 'Nigeria's PPP Framework: Deploying Subnational PPPs Towards Remediating a National Infrastructure Deficit' <https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3718774> accessed on March 17, 2026

¹⁰ ibid

generation, ports, and housing. Notable examples include the Lekki–Epe Expressway concession, the Azura-Edo Independent Power Project, and the Highway Development and Management Initiative (HDMI).¹¹

2.1.2 Risk Allocation in PPP Projects

Risk allocation refers to the contractual distribution of responsibilities for managing project risks between parties to a PPP agreement.¹² It means deciding which party to the PPP contract will bear the cost or reap the benefit of a change in project outcomes arising from each risk factor.¹³ Risk is inherent in infrastructure development because such projects typically involve large capital investments, long concession periods, and complex technical requirements. The success of PPP projects depends largely on allocating each risk to the party best able to manage it effectively and at the least cost.¹⁴ This principle is widely recognised as the fundamental rule governing risk allocation in PPP contracts. Precisely, the fundamental principles of risk allocation in PPP contracts surmises that risks must be allocated to the party best able to control the likelihood of the risk occurring, best able to control the impact of the risk on project outcomes and best able to absorb the risk at lowest cost.¹⁵ Site risks arise from uncertainties relating to land conditions, environmental hazards, geological factors, and the presence of archaeological artefacts. These risks can significantly affect construction timelines and project costs.

2.1.3 Archaeological Discovery Risk

Archaeological discovery risk arises when artefacts, monuments, burial sites, or other cultural heritage resources are discovered during construction activities. Such discoveries

¹¹ Infrastructure Concession Regulatory Commission, 'Highway Development Management Initiative Launched' < [https://www.icrc.gov.ng/highway-development-management-initiative-launched/#:~:text=The%20Highway%20Development%20Management%20Initiative%20\(HDMI\)%20is,technical%20expertise%2C%20managerial%20capacity%2C%20and%20financial%20resources](https://www.icrc.gov.ng/highway-development-management-initiative-launched/#:~:text=The%20Highway%20Development%20Management%20Initiative%20(HDMI)%20is,technical%20expertise%2C%20managerial%20capacity%2C%20and%20financial%20resources)> accessed on March 17, 2026

¹² E.R. Yescombe, *Public-Private Partnerships: Principles of Policy and Finance* (2nd edn, Butterworths 2011).

¹³ World Bank Public-Private Resource Centre, 'Allocating Risk' < <https://ppp.worldbank.org/allocating-risks#:~:text=Allocating%20risk%2C%20in%20the%20context,are%20not%20happy%20to%20bear.>> accessed on March 17, 2026

¹⁴ Yescombe (n12)

¹⁵ Irwin, Timothy C. 2007. *Government Guarantees: Allocating and Valuing Risk in Privately Financed Infrastructure Projects*. Directions in Development. Washington, DC: World Bank. [#970]

may halt construction, trigger legal obligations requiring excavation, preservation, or relocation of the discovered artefacts.¹⁶ In many jurisdictions, heritage protection laws require immediate suspension of construction works once archaeological artefacts are discovered. The discovery may therefore lead to project delays, additional excavation costs, redesign of infrastructure routes, and possible compensation claims by contractors.¹⁷ In Nigeria, archaeological resources are protected under the National Commission for Museums and Monuments Act, which empowers the National Commission for Museums and Monuments to preserve cultural heritage sites.¹⁸ Under this legislation, the discovery of archaeological artefacts during construction may require investigation or preservation measures before work can resume.¹⁹ Because archaeological discoveries are typically unforeseen and difficult to predict through preliminary site investigations, they are often classified as “unforeseen site conditions” or “latent conditions” in infrastructure contracts.²⁰

2.2 Theoretical Framework

2.2.1 Economic Efficiency Theory

Economic efficiency theory forms the primary conceptual basis for risk allocation in PPP projects. According to this theory, risks should be optimally allocated to the party best able to manage them efficiently and at the lowest cost. This principle is widely recognised in international PPP guidelines and is reflected in the World Bank PPP Reference Guide, which emphasises that optimal risk allocation enhances project efficiency and reduces overall costs.²¹ Applying this theory to archaeological discovery risk suggests that such risks should be borne by the party that can best manage the legal, financial, and operational implications of the discovery. Private concessionaires typically control construction

¹⁶ UNESCO, Operational Guidelines for the Implementation of the World Heritage Convention (2021) <<https://whc.unesco.org/en/guidelines/>> accessed on March 18, 2026

¹⁷ World Bank, Public-Private Partnerships Reference Guide (3rd edn, 2017) <<https://ppp.worldbank.org/PPP-Reference-Guide>> accessed on March 18, 2026

¹⁸ Section 3 National Commission for Museums and Monuments Act Cap N19 Laws of the Federation of Nigeria 2004.

¹⁹ Ibid section 20

²⁰ Jeffery Delmon, *Private Sector Investment in Infrastructure: Project Finance, PPP Projects and PPP Frameworks* (2nd edn, Kluwer Law International 2009)

²¹ World Bank, *PPP Reference Guide* (2017).

activities and may therefore appear to be better positioned to manage construction-related risks. However, archaeological preservation obligations are imposed by the state in pursuit of public interest objectives such as heritage conservation. Consequently, the government may be better positioned to manage such risks through regulatory coordination and public funding.

2.2.2 Incomplete Contract Theory

The concept of unforeseen site conditions (including archaeological discoveries) fits squarely within the framework of incomplete contract theory, which recognised that it is impossible for parties to anticipate and provide for every future contingency in a contract.²² Archaeological risk falls within the broader category of unforeseen site conditions or latent defects, which are inherently difficult to predict even with extensive due diligence. Standard international contracting practice particularly under FIDIC²³ forms (under Clause 4.12) allocates such risks to the employer (i.e., the public authority), on the basis that such risks are not reasonably foreseeable by contractors. This principle is reinforced in construction law jurisprudence. In *Obrascon Huarte Lain SA v Her Majesty's Attorney General for Gibraltar*,²⁴ the court emphasised that while contractors must exercise due diligence, they are not expected to anticipate truly unforeseeable conditions beyond reasonable investigation.

From a jurisprudential standpoint, this aligns with the broader doctrines of fairness and risk distribution. The rule in *Rylands v Fletcher*²⁵ establishes that a party who, for their own purposes, brings onto land and accumulates a potentially hazardous or disruptive thing is strictly liable for damage resulting from its escape, provided that the use of the land is “non-natural.” The underlying rationale is one of risk allocation based on control and enterprise: the party who introduces or benefits from a potentially risky activity should bear the consequences of that risk, even in the absence of fault. Although archaeological

²² Philippe Aghio & Richard Holden, ‘*Incomplete Contracts and the Theory of the Firm: What Have We Learned Over the Past 25 Years?*’ *Journal of Economic Perspectives* (vol 25) (No.2) (2011) pp. 181-197

²³ International Federation of Consulting Engineers is a global representative body for consulting engineers founded in 1913. It is best known for developing standardized, balanced, and widely used construction contract forms for large-scale international infrastructure projects

²⁴ UK Court of Appeal [2015] EWCA CIV 712

²⁵ (1868) LR 3 HL 330

artefacts do not “escape” in the traditional sense contemplated in *Rylands v Fletcher*, the principle is instructive by analogy. In a road PPP context, the public authority initiates and authorises the infrastructure development, effectively altering the use of land and triggering excavation activities that may expose buried cultural heritage. The discovery of archaeological materials is therefore a direct consequence of the project itself. As between the contracting parties, the public authority is better positioned to bear this risk for several reasons. First, it has sovereign control over land use and access to national heritage data and regulatory institutions. Second, archaeological preservation is fundamentally a matter of public interest and policy, rather than a purely commercial construction risk. Third, allocating such risk to the contractor would either lead to inflated bid prices (as contractors price in uncertainty) or inefficient risk transfer where the contractor lacks the capacity to manage the consequences. Accordingly, while the strict liability framework in *Rylands v Fletcher* is not directly applicable, its underlying principle that risk should lie with the party who introduces or benefits from the activity giving rise to that risk supports the allocation of archaeological discovery risk to the public authority in PPP infrastructure projects.

2.2.3 Principal–Agent Theory

Principal–agent theory also provides useful insights into PPP risk allocation. In PPP arrangements, the government acts as the principal, while the private sector entity acts as the agent responsible for delivering infrastructure services. The theory emphasises the importance of structuring contracts in a way that aligns the incentives of the private agent with the public objectives of the principal.²⁶ In the context of archaeological discoveries, the government has a statutory duty to protect cultural heritage resources.²⁷ Assigning full responsibility for such discoveries to private concessionaires may undermine this public policy objective or lead to underreporting of archaeological finds by contractors seeking to avoid delays. Therefore, principal-agent theory suggests that government involvement in managing archaeological discoveries may produce better outcomes for heritage protection.

²⁶ Torben Bernhold & Niklas Weisweg, ‘Principal-Agent Theory Perspectives and Practices for Effective Workplace Solution’ < https://www.researchgate.net/publication/353637721_PRINCIPAL-AGENT_THEORY_Perspectives_and_practices_for_effective_workplace_solutions > accessed on March 18, 2026

²⁷ Section 3, National Commission for Museums and Monuments Act

2.3 Literature Review

Scholarly literature on PPP infrastructure projects has extensively examined the issue of risk allocation, although relatively few studies focus specifically on archaeological discovery risk. Yescombe argues that the viability of PPP projects depends heavily on the allocation of risks between contracting parties and warns that transferring risks beyond the control of private investors may undermine project bankability.²⁸ Similarly, Delmon notes that unforeseeable site conditions represent a significant risk in infrastructure development and are often addressed through contractual compensation mechanisms rather than full risk transfer to private investors.²⁹ The World Bank PPP Reference Guide also emphasises that risks relating to land acquisition, environmental protection, and cultural heritage are typically retained by the public sector because they involve broader public policy considerations.³⁰

Although Nigerian case law on archaeological risk is limited, comparative jurisprudence provides strong guidance. In *Crossrail v Skanska*³¹, Roman archaeological remains discovered during tunnelling works led to delays. The tribunal held that the discovery constituted an unforeseeable condition and the contractor was entitled to an extension of time and partial cost compensation. Similarly, in *Humber Oil Terminals Trustee Ltd v Associated British Port*³² archaeological findings triggered delays, failure of construction equipment and time risk was shifted to the employer, while cost allocation was shared. These cases demonstrate a consistent principle that archaeological risk is treated as an employer/public sector risk subject to contractual adjustments. This is justified on the grounds that government controls heritage regulation, archaeological discoveries cannot reliably be assessed at a tender state and cultural heritage protection is a sovereign responsibility.

²⁸ Yescombe(n 9)

²⁹ Delmon (n 12)

³⁰ World Bank (n 5)

³¹ [2018] UK Arbitration

³² [2011] EWHC 2043

3 CHAPTER THREE

LEGAL AND INSTITUTIONAL FRAMEWORK FOR PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIPS IN NIGERIA

3.1 Legal Framework

3.1.1 Infrastructure Concession Regulatory Commission Act 2005

The Infrastructure Concession Regulatory Commission Act 2005 (ICRC Act) constitutes the primary legislation governing PPP arrangements at the federal level in Nigeria. The Act was enacted to promote private sector participation in infrastructure development and to establish a regulatory framework for concession agreements between the Federal Government and private investors.³³ Under section 1 of the Act, the Federal Government may enter into concession agreements with private entities for the financing, construction, operation, or maintenance of infrastructure facilities. Such infrastructure includes highways, bridges, railways, power facilities, ports, and other public assets. The Act also mandates that concession agreements must clearly define the rights, obligations, and risk allocation arrangements between the contracting parties.³⁴ This requirement is particularly important because PPP projects involve complex contractual arrangements in which multiple categories of risks must be allocated between the public authority and the private concessionaire. Although the Act does not expressly address archaeological discovery risk, it provides the legal basis for incorporating contractual provisions dealing with unforeseen site conditions, which may include archaeological discoveries encountered during construction.

3.1.2 National Commission for Museums and Monuments Act 1979

The National Commission for Museums and Monuments Act (NCMM Act) is the principal legislation governing the protection of cultural heritage and archaeological resources in Nigeria.³⁵ Under the Act, monuments, relics, and archaeological artefacts are recognised

³³ Section 1 ICRC Act

³⁴ *ibid*

³⁵ National Commission for Museums and Monuments Act Cap N19 Laws of the Federation of Nigeria 2004.

as part of Nigeria's national heritage and are subject to legal protection.³⁶ The Act prohibits the destruction, alteration, or removal of protected monuments without the authorisation of the Commission.³⁷ Where archaeological artefacts are discovered, notice must be given to the Commission and the Commission may require excavation, preservation, or documentation of the site.³⁸ In the context of infrastructure construction, the discovery of archaeological artefacts may therefore trigger statutory obligations requiring the suspension of construction activities until appropriate archaeological investigations are carried out. These statutory obligations are significant for PPP projects because they introduce regulatory risks that may affect construction timelines and project costs. Since the obligation to preserve cultural heritage arises from government legislation, the risk associated with archaeological discoveries may arguably fall within the regulatory responsibilities of the state.

3.1.3 Environmental Impact Assessment Act 1992

Environmental regulation also plays an important role in infrastructure development and PPP projects in Nigeria. The Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) Act requires that major development projects undergo environmental impact assessments before construction can commence.³⁹ Environmental impact assessments are designed to identify potential environmental and social impacts associated with proposed infrastructure projects. These assessments may include evaluations of ecological resources, land use patterns, and cultural heritage sites.⁴⁰ Where potential archaeological resources are identified during the assessment process, mitigation measures may be implemented to protect such resources before construction begins. However, despite environmental assessments, it is still possible for archaeological artefacts to be discovered during construction due to the inherent uncertainty associated with subsurface conditions.

³⁶ Section 19 NCMM Act

³⁷ Section 20(1) NCMM Act

³⁸ Section 20(2) NCMM Act

³⁹ Section 2 EIA Act

⁴⁰ Section 3 EIA Act

3.1.4 Land Use Act 1978

Land acquisition and land use regulation also influence PPP infrastructure projects in Nigeria. The Land Use Act 1978 vests all land within each state of the federation in the Governor of the state to be held in trust for the people.⁴¹ Under the Act, government authorities may acquire land for public purposes⁴², including infrastructure development. However, such acquisition must comply with statutory procedures and may involve compensation payments to affected landowners. Land use regulation is relevant to archaeological discoveries because the discovery of heritage artefacts may affect land development plans or require modifications to infrastructure routes. Where a significant archaeological site is discovered, government authorities may decide to preserve the site as a protected monument, thereby requiring adjustments to the infrastructure project.

3.2 Institutional Framework

3.2.1 The Infrastructure Concession Regulatory Commission (ICRC)

The ICRC is established under section 14 of the ICRC Act. It serves as the central coordinating body for federal PPP projects. The Commission reviews and approves concession agreements and monitors compliance with PPP regulations. The Commission is tasked with regulating, monitoring, and supervising concession agreements entered into by Ministries, Departments, and Agencies (MDAs) of the Federal Government.⁴³ Furthermore, the ICRC has issued PPP regulatory guidelines that encourage the adoption of international best practices in risk allocation and contract management. These guidelines emphasise the principle that risks should be allocated to the party best able to manage them effectively.

3.2.2 National Commission for Museums and Monuments

The NCMM Act establishes the National Commission for Museums and Monuments and empowers it to preserve and protect Nigeria's cultural heritage.⁴⁴ The Commission is

⁴¹ Section 1 LUA 1978

⁴² Section 51 LUA 1978

⁴³ Section 20 ICRC Act

⁴⁴ Section 1 NCMM Act

responsible for identifying, preserving, and regulating access to cultural resources. In the course of a construction, where archaeological artefacts are discovered, notice must be given to the Commission and the Commission may require excavation, preservation, or documentation of the site.⁴⁵

3.2.3 Federal Ministry of Lands, Housing and Urban Development

The Federal Ministry of Lands, Housing and Urban Development plays a critical role in road PPP projects in Nigeria, particularly in relation to land acquisition, title security, and the delivery of right-of-way, which are essential to project execution and bankability. The Ministry facilitates this process, including compensation and resettlement where existing interests are affected, in line with statutory requirements. The importance of proper land administration has been affirmed by the courts in *Adole v Gwar*⁴⁶, which underscores the Governor's control over land allocation, and *Osho v Foreign Finance Corporation*⁴⁷, which recognises rights of occupancy as the legally enforceable interest in land. Within the PPP framework, these functions translate into the allocation of land-related risks such as delays in site possession and title defects to the public sector, as the government is best positioned to manage such risks.

3.2.4 The National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (NESREA)

NESREA is Nigeria's primary federal agency responsible for enforcing environmental laws, standards, and regulations. Operating under the Federal Ministry of Environment, NESREA ensures compliance through monitoring, permitting, and developing regulations to protect Nigeria's natural resources.

⁴⁵ Section 20(2) NCMM Act

⁴⁶ (2008) 11 NWLR (Pt 1099) 562 (SC).

⁴⁷ (1991) 4 NWLR (Pt 184) 157 (SC).

4 CHAPTER FOUR

CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF RISK ALLOCATION IN RELATION TO ARCHAEOLOGICAL DISCOVERY IN NIGERIAN ROAD PPP PROJECTS

4.1 Principles Governing Risk Allocation in PPP Infrastructure Projects

Risk allocation in PPP projects is governed by several widely accepted principles developed through international infrastructure finance practice. The most fundamental principle is that risks should be allocated to the party best able to manage them efficiently and at the lowest cost.⁴⁸ According to Yescombe, efficient risk allocation ensures that each party bears only those risks that it has the capacity to control or mitigate.⁴⁹ Improper allocation of risks may increase the cost of infrastructure financing or discourage private sector participation in PPP projects. This principle is equally reflected within the Nigerian PPP framework. The ICRC, in its National Policy on PPP, emphasises that optimal risk allocation is critical to achieving value for money and bankability in PPP projects.⁵⁰ Nigerian scholarship further supports this position. Ayansola and Abiru observe that improper risk allocation remains a key challenge in Nigeria's PPP landscape, often resulting in increased project costs, renegotiations, or project failure.⁵¹ Similarly, Bontur Lugard, in his analysis of the Murtala Mohammed Airport Terminal 2 concession, identifies poor risk allocation as a major factor undermining PPP project outcomes in Nigeria.⁵²

In practice, construction risks are typically transferred to the private concessionaire because the private contractor controls the design and construction process. Conversely, political and regulatory risks are usually retained by the public authority because they arise from government actions or policy decisions. Archaeological discovery risk falls within the broader category of unforeseen site conditions, which represent one of the most difficult

⁴⁸ World Bank, *Public-Private Partnership Reference Guide* (3rd edn, World Bank 2017).

⁴⁹ E.R. Yescombe, *Public-Private Partnerships: Principles of Policy and Finance* (2nd edn, Butterworths 2011).

⁵⁰ Infrastructure Concession Regulatory Commission, *National Policy on Public Private Partnerships* (Federal Government of Nigeria, 2009).

⁵¹ Oluwaseun Ayansola and Mayowa Abiru, 'Nigeria's PPP Framework: Deploying Subnational PPPs Towards Remediating a National Infrastructure Deficit' <https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3718774> accessed March 26, 2026

⁵² Lugard, (n7)

risks to allocate in infrastructure contracts. Such risks arise when subsurface conditions differ from those anticipated during project planning. In Nigeria, the challenge is exacerbated by the limited availability of reliable geological and archaeological data, as well as institutional capacity constraints, which increase uncertainty and complicate effective risk allocation.⁵³

4.2 Nature of Archaeological Discovery Risk

Archaeological discovery risk refers to the possibility that previously unknown cultural heritage artefacts, burial grounds, historical monuments, or relics may be discovered during excavation or construction works. Such discoveries present unique challenges because they involve not only technical construction issues but also legal obligations arising from heritage protection laws. In most jurisdictions, cultural heritage legislation requires that construction activities be suspended when archaeological artefacts are discovered so that appropriate investigations can be conducted.⁵⁴ The discovery of archaeological artefacts may therefore result in suspension of construction works, archaeological excavation and documentation, redesign or relocation of infrastructure facilities, increased project costs and delays in project completion.⁵⁵ Because archaeological discoveries are typically unpredictable despite preliminary site investigations, they are often considered force majeure or compensation events in infrastructure contracts.⁵⁶

4.3 International Approaches to Archaeological Discovery Risk

4.3.1 United Kingdom

In the United Kingdom, PPP infrastructure projects are commonly structured using the Private Finance Initiative (PFI) model. Under standard PFI contracts, archaeological

⁵³ Delmon (n 20)

⁵⁴ UNESCO, *Operational Guidelines for the Implementation of the World Heritage Convention* (2021) <https://whc.unesco.org/en/guidelines/>;

National Commission for Museums and Monuments Act Cap N19 Laws of the Federation of Nigeria 2004.

⁵⁵ World Bank, *Public-Private Partnership Reference Guide* (3rd edn, 2017) <https://ppp.worldbank.org/public-private-partnership/library/ppp-reference-guide-version-3>;

⁵⁶ International Federation of Consulting Engineers, *Conditions of Contract for Construction* (2nd edn, 2017) cl 4.12 (Unforeseeable Physical Conditions); Delmon, (n20).

discoveries encountered during construction are typically treated as compensation events.⁵⁷ This means that if archaeological artefacts are discovered, the contractor may be entitled to additional time or compensation for delays caused by archaeological investigations.⁵⁸ The rationale for this approach is that cultural heritage preservation is primarily a public policy responsibility of government rather than a commercial construction risk.⁵⁹

4.3.2 Australia

Australian infrastructure contracts often contain “latent condition clauses” that address unforeseen subsurface conditions encountered during construction.⁶⁰ These clauses allow contractors to claim additional payment or time extensions where subsurface conditions differ materially from those anticipated in the contract. Archaeological discoveries are frequently treated as latent conditions because they cannot be reasonably predicted through ordinary site investigations.

4.3.3 South Africa

South Africa provides a particularly relevant comparator for Nigeria because both countries share similar legal traditions and infrastructure development challenges. Under South Africa's PPP Manual issued by the National Treasury, risks relating to land acquisition, environmental approvals, and cultural heritage preservation are typically retained by the public authority.⁶¹ Hence where archaeological artefacts are discovered during construction, the government may assume responsibility for coordinating archaeological investigations and compensating the contractor for resulting delays.

⁵⁷ HM Treasury, *Standardisation of PFI Contracts (SoPC4)* (2007) https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/221556/standardisation_of_pfi_contracts_v4_ogc.pdf

⁵⁸ International Federation of Consulting Engineers, *Conditions of Contract for Construction* (2nd edn, 2017) cl 4.12 (Unforeseeable Physical Conditions); E.R. Yescombe, *Public-Private Partnerships: Principles of Policy and Finance* (2nd edn, Butterworth-Heinemann 2011).

⁵⁹ World Bank, *Public-Private Partnership Reference Guide* (3rd edn, 2017) <https://ppp.worldbank.org/public-private-partnership/library/ppp-reference-guide-version-3>; Jeffrey Delmon, *Private Sector Investment in Infrastructure* (2nd edn, Kluwer Law International 2009).

⁶⁰ Delmon, (n 4).

⁶¹ National Treasury (South Africa), *Public-Private Partnership Manual*.

4.4 Nigerian Infrastructure PPP Case Studies

4.4.1 Lekki–Epe Expressway Concession

The **Lekki–Epe Expressway concession** represents one of Nigeria's earliest and most prominent road PPP projects. The project involved a concession agreement between the Lagos State Government and the Lekki Concession Company for the financing, construction, and operation of the expressway. Although the project was innovative in its financing structure, it faced significant challenges including public opposition to tolling and financial restructuring of the concession agreement.⁶² While archaeological discovery was not a central issue in the project, the concession highlights the importance of clearly defined risk allocation provisions in PPP agreements. The project demonstrated that poorly structured risk allocation can lead to disputes between government authorities and private investors.

4.4.2 Azura–Edo Independent Power Project

Although not a road project, the Azura–Edo Independent Power Project provides a useful example of effective risk allocation in Nigerian infrastructure development. The project successfully attracted international financing largely because risks were carefully distributed among various stakeholders including the Federal Government, private investors, and international financial institutions.⁶³ Regulatory and political risks were largely assumed by the government through various guarantees and contractual protections, thereby improving investor confidence. The success of the Azura–Edo project demonstrates the importance of allocating risks to the party best able to manage them.

4.4.3 Highway Development and Management Initiative (HDMI)

⁶² Augustine Edobor Arimoro, 'Impact of community stakeholders on public-private partnerships: Lessons from the Lekki-Epe concession toll road' <
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/281286284_Impact_of_community_stakeholders_on_public-private_partnerships_Lessons_from_the_Lekki-Epe_concession_toll_road> accessed March 18, 2026

⁶³ World Bank Group, 'Nigeria: The Azura-Edo Independent Power Plant' <
https://ppp.worldbank.org/sites/default/files/2022-02/NigeriaAzuraIPP_WBG.pdf> accessed on March 18, 2026

The Federal Government's Highway Development and Management Initiative (HDMI) aims to concession major federal highways to private investors under PPP arrangements.⁶⁴ The initiative recognises the need for clearly structured risk allocation frameworks in order to attract private sector participation in highway development.⁶⁵ Although HDMI concession agreements are still evolving, they provide an opportunity to incorporate international best practices in risk allocation, including provisions addressing unforeseen site conditions and archaeological discoveries.

4.5 Legal Basis for Allocating Archaeological Discovery Risk in Nigeria

The Nigerian legal framework provides compelling grounds for allocating archaeological discovery risk primarily to the public authority, or at the minimum treating it as a shared risk rather than one borne solely by the private concessionaire. This position is rooted in statutory obligations, institutional competence and broader public policy considerations.

First, the NCMM Act establishes a clear legal regime for the protection and preservation of cultural heritage in Nigeria. Under the Act, the NCMM is vested with the authority to declare, protect, and manage national monuments and antiquities.⁶⁶ Crucially, the Act imposes obligations that are inherently public in nature, including the preservation, excavation, and regulation of cultural artefacts. These obligations are not contractual in origin and cannot be delegated wholesale to private entities through PPP arrangements. Hence where archaeological artefacts are discovered during construction, the statutory framework requires regulatory intervention, thereby removing decision-making authority from the private contractor.⁶⁷ This reinforces the conclusion that archaeological risk is not a purely commercial construction risk but a regulatory and sovereign responsibility.

Secondly, environmental regulations such as the EIA Act mandates that all major infrastructure projects undergo environmental and social impact assessments prior to

⁶⁴ Infrastructure Concession Regulatory Commission (n11)

⁶⁵ *ibid*

⁶⁶ National Commission for Museums and Monuments Act Cap N19 Laws of the Federation of Nigeria 2004

⁶⁷ *ibid*

commencement.⁶⁸ These assessments are required to identify and mitigate potential environmental and cultural impacts, including the presence of archaeological resources. However, in practice, environmental impact assessments in Nigeria often suffer from data limitations and do not always capture subsurface or previously unknown heritage resources.⁶⁹ Consequently, archaeological discoveries frequently arise despite compliance with pre-construction due diligence. Given that the obligation to conduct and approve environmental impact assessments rests with government authorities, it is consistent with principles of fairness and efficiency that the residual risk of undiscovered archaeological resources should also be borne, at least in part, by the public authority.

Third, archaeological preservation serves a broader societal interest that extends beyond the commercial objectives of private concessionaires. The preservation of cultural heritage contributes to national identity, historical research, and tourism development, making its protection a matter of public interest.⁷⁰ These considerations reinforce the argument that archaeological risk should remain within the domain of public authorities, as private concessionaires may lack both the incentive and institutional mandate to prioritise heritage preservation where it conflicts with project timelines or profitability. From an institutional standpoint, private concessionaires lack the legal authority to determine the treatment of archaeological discoveries. Decisions regarding excavation, preservation, relocation, or designation of heritage sites fall within the statutory mandate of the NCMM.⁷¹ This institutional asymmetry further supports the conclusion that archaeological risk cannot be efficiently allocated solely to private parties.

The practical realities of Nigerian PPP projects further underscore the importance of appropriate risk allocation. The Lekki–Epe Expressway Concession illustrates how deficiencies in risk allocation and stakeholder management can lead to significant project challenges, including public opposition, renegotiation, and financial restructuring.⁷²

⁶⁸ Environmental Impact Assessment Act Cap E12 Laws of the Federation of Nigeria 2004.

⁶⁹ Ayansola and Abiru (n51)

⁷⁰ UNESCO (n54)

⁷¹ S.3 NCMM Act

⁷² Arimoro (n 62)

Although archaeological risk was not central to the project, it highlights the broader consequences of misallocating risks tied to public interest considerations. In contrast, the Azura-Edo Independent Power Project demonstrates the importance of carefully structured risk allocation aligned with international best practices, which contributed to the project's bankability and success.⁷³ International PPP practice further supports the treatment of archaeological discoveries as compensation events rather than contractor risks. Standard forms such as FIDIC Conditions of Contract recognise unforeseen physical conditions, including archaeological finds, as grounds for time and cost relief. This approach reflects the principle that such risks are not reasonably foreseeable and cannot be efficiently managed by contractors.

Accordingly, the most appropriate approach in Nigerian road PPP projects is to treat archaeological discovery risk as a shared risk, managed through contractual compensation mechanisms. Under this framework, the contractor would be required to exercise due diligence, report discoveries promptly, and suspend construction where necessary. The public authority would assume responsibility for archaeological investigations, regulatory approvals, and preservation decisions, while compensating the contractor for delays and additional costs. This approach aligns with Nigerian statutory obligations, institutional realities, and international best practice, while promoting fairness, efficiency, and project bankability.

⁷³ World Bank (n 63)

5 CHAPTER FIVE

CHALLENGES AND PROSPECTS FOR EFFECTIVE RISK ALLOCATION IN NIGERIAN ROAD PPP PROJECTS

5.1 Institutional and Regulatory Challenges

One of the most significant challenges affecting PPP implementation in Nigeria is the limited institutional capacity of regulatory agencies responsible for overseeing infrastructure projects. Although the ICRC has been established to regulate PPP projects at the federal level, many government agencies still lack the technical expertise required to negotiate complex infrastructure contracts, particularly in areas such as project finance and risk allocation.⁷⁴ In addition, coordination among various regulatory institutions remains a challenge. PPP infrastructure projects typically involve multiple regulatory agencies, including the Federal Ministry of Works, environmental regulators, and heritage protection authorities such as the National Commission for Museums and Monuments.⁷⁵ The involvement of multiple regulatory bodies may create delays in decision-making processes, particularly when archaeological artefacts are discovered during construction and approvals are required from several agencies.⁷⁶

5.2 Lack of Comprehensive Pre-Construction Surveys

A key challenge in PPP implementation in Nigeria is the limited availability of reliable geological and archaeological data prior to project commencement. The absence of detailed site investigations makes it difficult to anticipate the likelihood of encountering archaeological artefacts during construction.⁷⁷ In contrast, many developed jurisdictions undertake comprehensive pre-construction archaeological and geotechnical surveys to identify potential heritage risks and incorporate mitigation measures into project planning.⁷⁸ The lack of such systematic surveys in Nigeria significantly increases

⁷⁴ Infrastructure Concession Regulatory Commission, (n1); (n48).

⁷⁵ Section 20 NCMM Act

⁷⁶ Jeffrey Delmon (n3); African Development Bank, *Nigeria PPP Market Study*.

⁷⁷ World Bank, (n48).

⁷⁸ UNESCO, *Operational Guidelines for the Implementation of the World Heritage Convention* (2021); Historic England, *Standard and Guidance for Archaeological Desk-Based Assessment* (2022).

uncertainty and complicates the effective allocation of archaeological discovery risk in PPP contracts.⁷⁹

5.3 Contractual Uncertainty in PPP Agreements

Another challenge relates to the lack of standardised PPP contract templates in Nigeria. Although the ICRC has issued PPP guidelines, concession agreements are often negotiated on a project-by-project basis, resulting to inconsistent approaches to risk allocation.⁸⁰ Clear contractual provisions dealing with archaeological discoveries are therefore essential for ensuring effective risk management in PPP projects.⁸¹

5.4 Prospects for Improving Risk Allocation

Notwithstanding the challenges identified, there are significant prospects for improving the management of archaeological discovery risk in Nigerian PPP infrastructure projects. The ongoing efforts of the ICRC to strengthen the PPP framework through the development of regulatory guidelines and standardised templates are likely to enhance consistency in risk allocation.⁸² In addition, the increasing involvement of international development finance institutions, such as the World Bank and the African Development Bank, has promoted the adoption of international best practices, particularly in relation to structured risk allocation and bankability requirements.⁸³ Furthermore, the experience derived from previous PPP projects in Nigeria provides a growing body of practical lessons that can be incorporated into future concession agreements, thereby improving project governance and the allocation of risks, including those arising from unforeseen site conditions.⁸⁴

⁷⁹ Jeffrey Delmon, (n3); African Development Bank (n76)

⁸⁰ Infrastructure Concession Regulatory Commission, (n1); World Bank, (n48).

⁸¹ E.R. Yescombe, *Public-Private Partnerships: Principles of Policy and Finance* (2nd edn, Butterworth-Heinemann 2011).

⁸² Infrastructure Concession Regulatory Commission, *National Policy on Public Private Partnership* (2009).

⁸³ World Bank, *Public-Private Partnership Reference Guide* (3rd edn, 2017); African Development Bank, *Nigeria PPP Market Study*.

⁸⁴ E.R. Yescombe, (n58); Jeffrey Delmon (n3).

6 CHAPTER SIX

FINDINGS, RECOMMENDATIONS AND CONCLUSION

6.1 Summary of Findings

Several important findings emerge from the analysis conducted in this research. First, the study finds that risk allocation is a central component of PPP infrastructure agreements and significantly influences the financial viability and sustainability of such projects. Second, archaeological discovery risk constitutes a unique category of infrastructure risk because it arises from statutory obligations relating to cultural heritage protection rather than ordinary construction activities. Third, Nigerian legislation such as the National Commission for Museums and Monuments Act imposes responsibilities on government authorities to preserve and protect archaeological resources. Fourth, comparative analysis of international PPP practices indicates that archaeological discoveries are typically treated as compensation events rather than risks fully transferred to private concessionaires. Finally, the study finds that transferring archaeological discovery risk entirely to private investors may discourage investment in infrastructure projects and increase project financing costs.

6.2 Recommendations

Based on the findings of this research, several recommendations are proposed.

- a. Incorporation of Archaeological Discovery Clauses in PPP Contracts PPP concession agreements in Nigeria should include explicit contractual provisions addressing archaeological discoveries during construction.
- b. Government Responsibility for Archaeological Investigations. Where archaeological artefacts are discovered, the government should assume responsibility for coordinating archaeological investigations through MCMM.
- c. Compensation Mechanisms for Contractors. PPP contracts should provide for compensation mechanisms where archaeological discoveries significantly delay construction activities. Compensation may include time extensions, cost reimbursements, or adjustments to concession periods.

- d. Comprehensive Pre-Construction Archaeological Surveys. Government authorities should conduct detailed archaeological surveys during the project planning stage. These surveys would help identify potential heritage sites before construction begins and reduce the likelihood of unexpected discoveries during project execution.
- e. Development of Standard PPP Contract Templates. The Infrastructure Concession Regulatory Commission should develop standardised PPP contract templates that include provisions for managing unforeseen site conditions, including archaeological discoveries.

6.3 Contribution to Knowledge

This study advances existing scholarship on PPPs by critically examining the allocation of archaeological discovery risk within the Nigerian infrastructure context, an area that has received limited scholarly attention. By situating such risk within the frameworks of optimal risk allocation and Incomplete Contract Theory, the study provides a doctrinal and theoretical basis for its classification as an unforeseeable site condition. It further bridges the gap between international best practices—particularly under International Federation of Consulting Engineers standards and guidance from the World Bank—and Nigeria’s domestic legal framework. In doing so, it offers a coherent analytical basis for allocating archaeological risk to the public sector, while proposing contractual mechanisms to enhance certainty, bankability, and regulatory compliance in PPP arrangements.

6.4 Areas for Further Study

Further research is warranted in several areas. Empirical studies are needed to evaluate how archaeological discovery risks are managed in practice across Nigerian PPP projects. In addition, the potential of emerging technologies, including geospatial and remote sensing tools, to mitigate such risks merits deeper investigation. Comparative analyses across jurisdictions would also enrich understanding of how institutional capacity influences risk allocation. Finally, further doctrinal research is required to examine the interface between cultural heritage regulation and infrastructure development, with a view to informing legal and policy reforms in Nigeria.

6.5 Conclusion

This study has examined the allocation of archaeological discovery risk in Nigerian road PPP projects and analysed the legal basis for determining which party should bear such risk. The analysis demonstrates that archaeological discovery risk differs fundamentally from ordinary construction risks because it arises from statutory obligations relating to cultural heritage protection. Nigerian legislation places primary responsibility for the preservation of archaeological resources on government authorities. Comparative analysis of international PPP practices further indicates that archaeological discoveries are typically treated as compensation events rather than risks fully transferred to private concessionaires. Accordingly, this study concludes that the public authority should bear primary responsibility for archaeological discovery risk in Nigerian road PPP projects, while contractual mechanisms should be established to compensate concessionaires for delays or additional costs arising from such discoveries. Adopting this approach would align Nigerian PPP practices with international standards, promote investor confidence, and ensure the effective preservation of Nigeria's cultural heritage.

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